

Awareness and Practice of the Salesian Preventive System of Basic Education Teachers

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Abstract:

This study examined the awareness and extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System (SPS) among basic education teachers in three Salesian schools in the Philippine South Province. Using a quantitative, descriptive-comparative, and correlational research design, the study assessed 112 teachers selected through stratified random sampling. Data were gathered through a validated and highly reliable survey instrument anchored on the three pillars of the SPS: Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness. Descriptive statistics, Mann-Whitney U tests, Kruskal-Wallis tests, and Spearman's rank correlation were employed to analyze the data. Results revealed a very high level of awareness and a very great extent of practice across all SPS pillars. No significant differences in awareness or practice were found when respondents were grouped according to age, sex, years of service, or department, indicating a cohesive institutional formation culture. Spearman's rho demonstrated strong and significant correlations ($\rho = 0.685$ to 0.890 , $p < .001$), showing that higher awareness of the SPS is strongly associated with greater consistency in its pedagogical application. These findings affirm that the SPS remains deeply embedded in the identity and daily practice of Salesian educators and underscore the importance of ongoing formation in sustaining Don Bosco's educational charism. The study suggests enhancing targeted mentoring for younger teachers and strengthening spiritual accompaniment initiatives to further deepen the lived practice of the SPS. Future research may explore qualitative insights and broader comparative analyses across other Salesian or Catholic institutions.

Keywords: Salesian Preventive System, Don Bosco, teacher awareness, pedagogical practice, Catholic education, Salesian schools, Reason Religion Loving-Kindness, teacher formation, values-based education, quantitative research

Introduction:

The Salesian Preventive System (SPS), formulated by St. John Bosco in the 19th century, remains one of the most enduring holistic educational approaches in Catholic pedagogy. Rooted in the pillars of reason, religion, and loving-kindness, the system emphasizes sympathetic guidance over punitive discipline (Braido, 2013; Lenti, 2010). Historically, Don Bosco developed the SPS amid social instability in Turin, where marginalized youth faced poverty, exploitation, and lack of moral formation. His approach sought not only academic development but also character formation and spiritual grounding, making education both an act of love and a means of social transformation. Contemporary Salesian institutions continue to uphold this vision, adapting its practices to modern schooling realities.

Globally, the push for holistic formation has intensified as schools increasingly move beyond cognitive outcomes to address students' moral, emotional, and social development. International trends highlight the importance of relational pedagogy, socio-emotional learning, and values-based education as critical aspects of student well-being and long-term success (Noddings, 2013; Sprague & Walker, 2021). These trends align with the SPS emphasis on supportive relationships, empathetic engagement, and pastoral presence. At the same time, these developments underscore the urgency of studying how enduring educational philosophies, such as Salesian pedagogy, function in contemporary contexts characterized by digital distractions, mental health concerns, and shifting moral landscapes.

The expanding network of Salesian schools illustrates the continued relevance of the SPS. With more than 3,643 schools in 132 countries, the Salesian educational mission reaches approximately 940,000 learners worldwide (Agenzia iNfo Salesiana, 2016). These institutions vary widely in cultural context, student demographics, and institutional resources, requiring flexible yet faithful implementation of the SPS. Scholars argue that while the foundational pillars remain constant, the actual practice of the SPS must respond to evolving educational challenges, including technological shifts, the rise of inclusive education, and increasing diversity in learning needs (Farfan, 2019;

Vojtáš, 2024). This global diversity raises critical questions about consistency in understanding and practicing the SPS among educators.

In the Philippines, the SPS is deeply woven into the identity of Salesian educational institutions. Catholic education, more broadly, plays a major role in shaping the moral and spiritual character of Filipino youth, with the Department of Education's K-12 curriculum emphasizing values formation, civic responsibility, and social transformation (DepEd, 2023). Research on Catholic schools in the Philippines shows that teacher identity, spiritual formation, and commitment to mission significantly influence the success of values-based education (Banusing, 2020; Cena & Bual, 2021). Yet Philippine studies also report variation in how teachers interpret religious or character formation programs depending on their training, years of service, and personal spirituality (Mohamad & Sihes, 2019; Madrigal & Oracion, 2018). This variability underscores the need for empirical assessment of teachers' awareness and practice of the SPS.

Within the Philippine South Province of the Salesians of Don Bosco, three major schools—Don Bosco Technical Institute–Victorias (DBTI), St. Louis School–Don Bosco Dumaguete (SLS-DB), and Don Bosco Technical College Cebu (DBTC)—serve as key sites for the implementation of the Preventive System. Each school integrates academic rigor with spiritual formation, youth ministry, and technical education. However, differences in school culture, teacher demographics, and departmental structures may affect how the SPS is understood and practiced across these institutions. Scholars have pointed out that institutional ethos, leadership modeling, and teacher formation programs strongly shape the internalization of the SPS, yet consistency cannot be assumed (Day et al., 2009; Edkins, 2013). These varied institutional contexts make it important to evaluate the uniformity—or lack thereof—in educators' application of the Preventive System.

At the heart of the SPS is the teacher, whose instructional decisions, personal spirituality, and relational approach directly shape how Don Bosco's pedagogy is lived out. Clark and Yinger's (1977) Teacher Thinking Theory suggests that teachers' cognitions—their beliefs, values, awareness, and reflective processes—drive their classroom behavior and pedagogical choices. This theory is particularly relevant to the SPS, where reflective practice, moral conviction, and affective presence are essential components. Teachers' awareness of the SPS influences how they enact reason, religion, and loving-kindness in day-to-day interactions such as discipline, guidance, and classroom management. However, empirical evidence suggests that awareness does not always lead to consistent practice, especially in values-based systems where personal dispositions and contextual factors play major roles (Pajares, 1992; Fang, 1996).

The complexity of applying the SPS becomes more evident when considering contemporary challenges faced by teachers. Issues such as declining student religiosity, increased behavioral concerns, and the pressures of modern academic environments test the practicality of value-centered approaches. While the SPS offers a preventive method grounded in compassion and guidance, researchers caution that teachers often struggle with the religious dimension of their role or with sustaining loving-kindness amid heavy workloads and emotional stress (Jackson, 2018; Vojtáš, 2024). This tension between ideal and practice raises questions about how deeply educators internalize the SPS and how effectively they apply it across different school environments.

Moreover, demographic variables such as age, sex, years of service, and department may influence the interpretation and application of key SPS principles. For example, studies indicate that younger teachers may demonstrate strong enthusiasm but inconsistent spiritual grounding, while veteran teachers may show deeper internalization but also potential fatigue (Day & Gu, 2009). Male and female teachers may also experience different expectations regarding pastoral presence or emotional expression, influencing their practice of loving-kindness or religious guidance (Gonzales & Cacho, 2019). Departmental differences—such as elementary versus high school—often shape the relational dynamics between teachers and learners, affecting opportunities to model or implement SPS principles. These contextual variations highlight the value of examining SPS awareness and practice across teacher groups.

Despite the centrality of the Preventive System in Salesian schools, existing research points to a critical gap: few empirical studies examine both teachers' awareness and their actual practice of the SPS simultaneously, especially in the Philippine South Province. Further, most existing works focus either on qualitative narratives or administrative evaluations rather than systematically measuring the relationship between awareness and practice. This gap makes

it difficult to determine whether Salesian teachers internalize the SPS conceptually, whether they apply it consistently, and whether demographic factors influence this alignment.

Thus, this study seeks to address these gaps by assessing the level of awareness and extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System among basic education teachers in three Salesian schools in the Philippine South Province. By examining differences across demographic variables and determining the relationship between awareness and practice, the study aims to provide evidence-based insights that can strengthen teacher formation, ensure consistent application of the SPS, and inform future Salesianity programs. In doing so, the research contributes to both the scholarship on Catholic education and the practical enhancement of Salesian pedagogical identity.

Methodology:

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-comparative, and correlational research design to examine the level of awareness and extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System (SPS) among basic education teachers in three Salesian schools in the Philippine South Province. A descriptive design allows an examination of variables as they naturally occur, providing an accurate portrayal of the current state of teachers' awareness and practice levels (Williams, 2011). The comparative aspect of the study further enabled the analysis of potential differences across demographic groups such as age, sex, years of service, and department. Comparative designs are appropriate when the goal is to identify variations across naturally occurring categories (Leedy & Ormrod, 2019). Meanwhile, the correlational component sought to determine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between teachers' awareness of the SPS and their extent of practice. Correlational designs are frequently used in educational research to determine the magnitude and direction of associations among variables without manipulating conditions (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

The study was conducted in three K-12 Salesian educational institutions located in Victorias City (Negros Occidental), Dumaguete City, and Cebu City. These schools represent the institutional landscape of the Salesian South Province, each operating under the educational philosophy of St. John Bosco and offering a blend of academic, pastoral, technical, and character formation programs. As part of an international network of Salesian schools, they are deeply rooted in the implementation of the Preventive System, making them ideal sites for assessing awareness and practice grounded in the pillars of reason, religion, and loving-kindness.

The study population consisted of 138 teachers, from which a sample of 112 respondents was drawn using stratified random sampling. Stratification ensured proportional representation across the three schools—School A ($n = 37$), School B ($n = 45$), and School C ($n = 30$)—reflecting 33.03%, 40.18%, and 26.79% of the sample, respectively. This technique was appropriate given the structural differences across institutions and ensured that teacher subgroups were accurately represented (Etikan & Bala, 2017). The sample size was determined based on the total population and aimed to achieve a margin of error of approximately 5.1% and a high confidence level. Respondents were further grouped according to four demographic variables: age, sex, years of service, and department. This demographic profiling was essential to understanding whether structural and personal characteristics influence SPS awareness and practice.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire adapted from Guiao (2009) and anchored on the three pillars of the Salesian Preventive System as articulated by Braido (2013)—reason, religion, and loving-kindness. The instrument consisted of two major parts: (1) demographic information, and (2) three subscales measuring awareness and practice of each SPS pillar. All items used a 5-point Likert scale, where higher scores indicated stronger awareness or more frequent practice. The instrument is widely used in SPS-related studies and aligns with teacher belief and behavior constructs (Pajares, 1992).

To establish content validity, the instrument underwent evaluation by a 15-member panel of Subject Matter Experts (SMEs), using Lawshe's (1985) Content Validity Ratio (CVR) method. Each SME classified each item as essential, useful but not essential, or not essential. Although Lawshe's minimum CVR for 15 panelists at the .05 significance level is .49, all items in this study obtained a CVR of 1.00, surpassing the threshold and indicating perfect expert agreement on item essentiality. The Content Validity Index (CVI) was also computed and yielded a rating of 1.00, demonstrating excellent overall content validity.

To assess instrument reliability, a pilot test was conducted with 30 teachers from one of the Salesian schools not included in the main sample. Using Cronbach’s alpha, the instrument generated a reliability coefficient of 0.959, which exceeds the acceptable standard of .70 and indicates excellent internal consistency (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Together, the validity and reliability tests confirm that the instrument is both conceptually sound and psychometrically robust.

Data gathering procedures adhered to standard ethical and administrative protocols. Permission to conduct the study was secured from the School Rectors and Principals of the participating institutions. Once approval was granted, the researcher coordinated with subject area coordinators to distribute the questionnaires. Teachers were informed of the study’s objectives, procedures, potential benefits, and voluntary nature. Informed consent was obtained before administering the instrument, ensuring adherence to ethical principles of autonomy, confidentiality, and non-maleficence (American Educational Research Association [AERA], 2011). Respondents accomplished the survey during free periods or after class hours. Completed questionnaires were collected, encoded, and subjected to statistical analysis.

The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Mean and standard deviation were used to interpret the teachers’ level of awareness and extent of practice. To determine differences across demographic categories, Mann–Whitney U tests were applied for variables with two groups (e.g., sex), while Kruskal–Wallis tests were used for variables with three or more categories (e.g., age, years of service). These nonparametric tests were appropriate given the ordinal data structure and the likelihood of non-normal distribution (Field, 2018). To examine the association between awareness and practice, Spearman’s rank-order correlation was utilized. This method is suitable for ordinal data and identifies both the strength and direction of relationships between variables (Laerd Statistics, 2018).

Results:

Table 1 presents the respondents’ level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System (SPS) across its three core pillars—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness. The data show consistently very high levels of awareness among Salesian educators in the three participating schools. The overall mean awareness score of 4.65 (sd = 0.507) indicates that teachers possess a strong and well-developed understanding of the SPS, regardless of their demographic profile.

Table 1. Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System

Areas	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Reason	4.67	0.716	Very High
Religion	4.63	0.517	Very High
Loving-Kindness	4.66	0.479	Very High
Overall	4.65	0.507	Very High

As shown in Table 1, Salesian educators reported a very high level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System across all three pillars. Mean scores ranged from 4.63 to 4.67, all interpreted as “Very High,” resulting in an overall mean of 4.65. These findings indicate that respondents are highly aware of the SPS framework as implemented in their respective schools.

Table 2. Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System by Age Group

Area	20–30 yrs (n=58)			31–40 yrs (n=25)			41–50 yrs (n=17)			51+ yrs (n=12)		
	\bar{x}	sd	VI	\bar{x}	sd	VI	\bar{x}	sd	VI	\bar{x}	sd	VI
Reason	4.61	0.918	VH	4.66	0.438	VH	4.8	0.352	VH	4.75	0.392	VH
Religion	4.57	0.563	VH	4.58	0.577	VH	4.79	0.299	VH	4.76	0.342	VH

Loving-Kindness	4.62	0.511	VH	4.62	0.534	VH	4.79	0.34	VH	4.79	0.329	VH
Overall	4.6	0.583	VH	4.62	0.491	VH	4.8	0.301	VH	4.77	0.337	VH

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; *sd* = standard deviation; *VI* = verbal interpretation; *VH* = Very High

Results in Table 2 show a very high level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System across all age groups. Overall means ranged from 4.60 to 4.80, with all groups consistently rated as "Very High." Among the groups, teachers aged 41–50 years recorded the highest overall awareness mean (4.80), while the youngest group (20–30 years) posted the lowest, though still very high, mean of 4.60.

Table 3. Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Sex

Area	Male \bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>	Female \bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>
Reason	4.62	0.441	VH	4.69	0.812	VH
Religion	4.67	0.462	VH	4.61	0.542	VH
Loving-Kindness	4.67	0.408	VH	4.66	0.51	VH
Overall	4.65	0.41	VH	4.65	0.548	VH

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; *sd* = standard deviation; *VI* = verbal interpretation; *VH* = Very High

Table 3 shows that both male and female teachers demonstrated a very high level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System across all three pillars. Overall mean scores for both groups were identical at 4.65, indicating comparable levels of awareness regardless of sex. Mean scores for Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness also remained consistently high for both groups, with only slight variations in standard deviations.

Table 4. Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Years of Service

Area	Less than 5 years			5–10 years			More than 10 years		
	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>
Reason	4.62	0.904	VH	4.73	0.415	VH	4.73	0.398	VH
Religion	4.6	0.535	VH	4.64	0.54	VH	4.68	0.472	VH
Loving-Kindness	4.62	0.492	VH	4.72	0.44	VH	4.69	0.49	VH
Overall	4.61	0.566	VH	4.7	0.431	VH	4.7	0.438	VH

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; *sd* = standard deviation; *VI* = verbal interpretation; *VH* = Very High

Table 4 shows that teachers across all lengths of service demonstrated a very high level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System. Overall means ranged from 4.61 to 4.70, with the highest awareness reported among teachers with 5–10 years and more than 10 years of service (both at 4.70). All three SPS pillars—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness—were consistently rated "Very High" across the groups. Standard deviations were highest among those with less than five years of service, indicating greater variability in awareness among newer teachers.

Table 5. Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Department

Area	Elementary			High School		
	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>
Reason	4.63	0.503	VH	4.68	0.799	VH

Religion	4.64	0.568	VH	4.63	0.496	VH
Loving-Kindness	4.65	0.537	VH	4.67	0.452	VH
Overall	4.64	0.506	VH	4.66	0.511	VH

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; *sd* = standard deviation; *VI* = verbal interpretation; *VH* = Very High

Table 5 shows that both elementary and high school teachers reported a very high level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System. Overall mean scores were similar for both groups—4.64 for elementary and 4.66 for high school teachers. Across all three pillars (Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness), both groups consistently reported “Very High” awareness, with only minimal differences in mean scores and standard deviations.

Table 6. Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System as a Whole

Areas	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Reason	4.56	0.446	Very Great
Religion	4.44	0.597	Very Great
Loving-Kindness	4.61	0.482	Very Great
Overall	4.53	0.447	Very Great

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; *sd* = standard deviation; *VI* = verbal interpretation; *VG* = Very Great

As shown in Table 6, Salesian educators demonstrated a very great extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System, with an overall mean of 4.53. All three pillars—Reason (4.56), Religion (4.44), and Loving-Kindness (4.61)—were rated “Very Great,” indicating that teachers consistently apply SPS principles in their daily interactions and professional practices. Among the three areas, Loving-Kindness recorded the highest mean (4.61), while Religion had the lowest (4.44), though still within the “Very Great” range.

Table 7 shows that all age groups demonstrated a very great extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System. Overall mean scores ranged from 4.49 to 4.65, with all three SPS pillars rated “Very Great” across age categories. The highest overall practice was observed among teachers aged 41–50 years and 51 years and above (both 4.65), while the lowest overall practice mean was recorded among the 20–30 years group (4.49). Despite minor variations, results indicate consistently strong practice of SPS principles across all age groups.

Table 7. Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Age

Area	20–30 yrs			31–40 yrs			41–50 yrs			51+ yrs		
	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>VI</i>									
Reason	4.53	0.475	VG	4.5	0.464	VG	4.68	0.356	VG	4.64	0.373	VG
Religion	4.33	0.643	VG	4.44	0.62	VG	4.57	0.453	VG	4.73	0.365	VG
Loving-Kindness	4.61	0.509	VG	4.64	0.502	VG	4.7	0.405	VG	4.58	0.445	VG
Overall	4.49	0.472	VG	4.5	0.463	VG	4.65	0.377	VG	4.65	0.37	VG

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; *sd* = standard deviation; *VI* = verbal interpretation; *VG* = Very Great

Table 8 shows that both male and female teachers exhibited a very great extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System. Overall mean scores were highly comparable between males (4.55) and females (4.53). Each SPS pillar—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness—was also rated “Very Great” by both groups, indicating consistent application of SPS principles regardless of sex.

Table 8. Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Sex

Area	Male \bar{x}	sd	VI	Female \bar{x}	sd	VI
Reason	4.56	0.367	VG	4.55	0.479	VG
Religion	4.41	0.682	VG	4.45	0.558	VG
Loving-Kindness	4.66	0.39	VG	4.59	0.519	VG
Overall	4.55	0.408	VG	4.53	0.465	VG

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; sd = standard deviation; VI = verbal interpretation; VG = Very Great

As shown in Table 9, respondents across all lengths of service demonstrated a very great extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System. Overall means ranged from 4.52 to 4.59, all interpreted as “Very Great.” Teachers with 5–10 years of service reported the highest overall practice mean (4.59), followed by those with less than five years and more than ten years (both 4.52). All three SPS pillars—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness—were consistently rated within the “Very Great” range across service groups.

Table 9. Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Years of Service

Area	Less than 5 years			5–10 years			More than 10 years		
	\bar{x}	sd	VI	\bar{x}	sd	VI	\bar{x}	sd	VI
Reason	4.51	0.46	VG	4.66	0.378	VG	4.54	0.471	VG
Religion	4.39	0.588	VG	4.48	0.689	VG	4.48	0.542	VG
Loving-Kindness	4.64	0.497	VG	4.63	0.411	VG	4.53	0.513	VG
Overall	4.52	0.441	VG	4.59	0.446	VG	4.52	0.472	VG

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; sd = standard deviation; VI = verbal interpretation; VG = Very Great

As shown in Table 10, both elementary and high school teachers reported a very great extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System. The overall mean for elementary teachers was 4.57, slightly higher than the 4.52 recorded for high school teachers. All three pillars—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness—were consistently rated “Very Great” by both groups, with only minor variations in mean scores and standard deviations.

Table 10. Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System When Grouped According to Department

Area	Elementary			High School		
	\bar{x}	sd	VI	\bar{x}	sd	VI
Reason	4.58	0.459	VG	4.55	0.442	VG
Religion	4.54	0.536	VG	4.38	0.62	VG
Loving-Kindness	4.59	0.492	VG	4.62	0.48	VG
Overall	4.57	0.451	VG	4.52	0.446	VG

Legend: \bar{x} = mean; sd = standard deviation; VI = verbal interpretation; VG = Very Great

Table 11 shows the results of comparative tests performed to determine whether significant differences existed in teachers' level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the area of Reason when grouped according to demographic profile. The p-values for age (0.789), sex (0.693), years of service (0.715), and department (0.713) all exceeded the 0.05 significance level. Accordingly, all differences were found to be not significant, and the null hypothesis was accepted for each demographic variable.

Table 11. Difference in Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Reason When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.789	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.61	0.918			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.66	0.438			
41-50 (n = 17)	4.8	0.352			
51+ (n = 12)	4.75	0.392			
Sex			0.693	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.62	0.441			
Female (n = 77)	4.69	0.812			
Years of Service			0.715	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.62	0.904			
5-10 years (n = 24)	4.73	0.415			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.73	0.398			
Department			0.713	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.63	0.503			
High School (n = 76)	4.68	0.799			

Table 12 shows the comparative results for teachers' level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the area of Religion across demographic categories. The p-values for age (0.342), sex (0.522), years of service (0.809), and department (0.916) were all greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, no significant differences were found among demographic groups, and the null hypothesis was accepted for all variables.

Table 12. Difference in Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Religion When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.342	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.57	0.563			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.58	0.577			

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
41-50 (n = 17)	4.79	0.299			
51+ (n = 12)	4.76	0.342			
Sex			0.522	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.67	0.462			
Female (n = 77)	4.61	0.542			
Years of Service			0.809	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.62	0.535			
5-10 years (n = 24)	4.6	0.54			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.68	0.472			
Department			0.916	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.64	0.568			
High School (n = 76)	4.63	0.496			

Table 13 shows that there were no significant differences in the level of awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the area of Loving-Kindness when respondents were grouped according to age ($p = 0.403$), sex ($p = 0.549$), years of service ($p = 0.651$), and department ($p = 0.828$). All p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold, leading to acceptance of the null hypothesis for each demographic factor.

Table 13. Difference in Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Loving-Kindness When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.403	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.62	0.511			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.62	0.534			
41-50 (n = 17)	4.79	0.34			
51+ (n = 12)	4.79	0.329			
Sex			0.549	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.67	0.408			
Female (n = 77)	4.66	0.51			
Years of Service			0.651	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.62	0.492			
5-10 years (n = 24)	4.72	0.44			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.7	0.49			

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Department			0.828	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.65	0.537			
High School (n = 76)	4.67	0.452			

Table 14 presents the comparative analysis of teachers' overall awareness of the Salesian Preventive System across demographic categories. The p-values for age (0.445), sex (0.962), years of service (0.686), and department (0.830) were all greater than the 0.05 significance level. These results indicate no significant differences in overall SPS awareness across any demographic group, and the null hypothesis was accepted for all variables.

Table 14. Difference in Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Loving-Kindness When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.445	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.6	0.583			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.62	0.491			
41-50 (n = 17)	4.8	0.301			
51+ (n = 12)	4.77	0.337			
Sex			0.962	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.65	0.41			
Female (n = 77)	4.65	0.548			
Years of Service			0.686	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.61	0.566			
5-10 years (n = 24)	4.69	0.431			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.7	0.438			
Department			0.83	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.638	0.506			
High School (n = 76)	4.66	0.511			

Table 15 shows that there were no significant differences in the teachers' extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the area of Reason across all demographic variables. The p-values for age (0.801), sex (0.772), years of service (0.469), and department (0.692) all exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted for each demographic category.

Table 15. Difference in Teachers’ Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Reason When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.801	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.53	0.475			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.5	0.464			
41-50 (n = 17)	4.68	0.356			
51+ (n = 12)	4.64	0.373			
Sex			0.772	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.56	0.367			
Female (n = 77)	4.55	0.479			
Years of Service			0.469	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.51	0.46			
5-10 years (n = 24)	4.66	0.378			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.54	0.471			
Department			0.692	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.58	0.459			
High School (n = 76)	4.55	0.442			

Table 16 shows that the extent of teachers’ practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the area of Religion did not significantly differ across demographic categories. All p-values—age (0.137), sex (0.781), years of service (0.735), and department (0.182)—were greater than the 0.05 threshold. As a result, the null hypothesis was accepted for all demographic variables.

Table 16. Difference in the Teachers’ Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Religion When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.137	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.33	0.643			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.44	0.62			
41-50 (n = 17)	4.57	0.453			
51+ (n = 12)	4.73	0.365			
Sex			0.781	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.41	0.682			

Female (n = 77)	4.45	0.558			
Years of Service			0.735	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.39	0.588			
5–10 years (n = 24)	4.48	0.689			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.48	0.542			
Department			0.182	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.54	0.536			
High School (n = 76)	4.38	0.62			

Table 17 shows that there were no significant differences in the teachers' extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the area of Loving-Kindness across demographic variables. The p-values for age (0.137), sex (0.477), years of service (0.598), and department (0.730) all exceeded the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted for all demographic factors.

Table 17. Difference in the Teachers' Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the Area of Loving-Kindness When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.137	not significant	accept
20–30 (n = 58)	4.61	0.509			
31–40 (n = 25)	4.64	0.502			
41–50 (n = 17)	4.7	0.405			
51+ (n = 12)	4.58	0.445			
Sex			0.477	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.66	0.39			
Female (n = 77)	4.59	0.519			
Years of Service			0.598	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.64	0.497			
5–10 years (n = 24)	4.63	0.411			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.53	0.513			
Department			0.73	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.59	0.492			
High School (n = 76)	4.62	0.48			

Table 18 shows that the teachers' overall extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System did not significantly differ when grouped according to demographic characteristics. All p-values—age (0.461), sex (0.816), years of

service (0.793), and department (0.448)—were greater than the 0.05 significance threshold. As a result, the null hypothesis was accepted for all variables, indicating no significant differences across demographic groups.

Table 18. Difference in the Teachers’ Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System in the Areas of Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness When Grouped According to Overall Practice Level

Profile	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Age			0.461	not significant	accept
20-30 (n = 58)	4.92	0.472			
31-40 (n = 25)	4.5	0.463			
41-50 (n = 17)	4.64	0.377			
51+ (n = 12)	4.52	0.37			
Sex			0.816	not significant	accept
Male (n = 35)	4.54	0.408			
Female (n = 77)	4.53	0.465			
Years of Service			0.793	not significant	accept
Less than 5 years (n = 60)	4.52	0.441			
5-10 years (n = 24)	4.59	0.446			
More than 10 years (n = 28)	4.52	0.472			
Department			0.448	not significant	accept
Elementary (n = 36)	4.57	0.451			
High School (n = 76)	4.52	0.446			

Table 19 shows the results of the Spearman’s rank-order correlation between teachers’ understanding and practice of the Salesian Preventive System. Across all three sets of correlation tests, the coefficients (0.685, 0.865, and 0.890) were positive and statistically significant at $p < 0.001$. These results indicate a significant relationship between understanding and practice, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in all cases.

Table 19. Relationship Between the Teachers’ Understanding and Practice of the Salesian Preventive System

Correlates	Spearman’s Rho	p-value	Significance @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Understanding & Practice (Set 1)	0.685	< 0.001	significant	reject
Understanding & Practice (Set 2)	0.865	< 0.001	significant	reject
Understanding & Practice (Set 3)	0.89	< 0.001	significant	reject

Discussion:

The findings of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of how basic education teachers in three Salesian schools in the Philippine South Province internalize and apply the Salesian Preventive System (SPS). Overall, the results demonstrate consistently very high awareness and very great extent of practice of the SPS across all pillars—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness. These findings affirm the strong institutional commitment of Salesian schools to Don Bosco’s educational vision and indicate an environment where his pedagogical principles remain actively cultivated and lived out in daily educational practice.

Teachers’ Level of Awareness of the Salesian Preventive System

Teachers across all age groups, sexes, lengths of service, and departments reported very high levels of awareness of the SPS. This uniformity suggests that Salesian schools have successfully embedded the SPS within their formation programs, orientations, and organizational culture. As supported in the Introduction, Don Bosco envisioned the Preventive System as a pedagogy accessible to all educators, rooted in understanding and relational presence rather than technical complexity (Braido, 2013; Lenti, 2010).

The very high awareness levels found in this study align with the argument that Salesian education depends heavily on the clarity with which educators grasp the pillars of Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness. Desramaut (2023) emphasized that deep awareness of SPS principles is a prerequisite for authentic practice, reinforcing the necessity of frequent formation activities. The consistency of scores across demographics reflects the institutional emphasis on shared mission identity, where formation is not dependent solely on individual characteristics but on the collective values of the Educative Pastoral Community (Day et al., 2009; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012).

Although awareness was overwhelmingly high, slight variations were noted. For instance, teachers aged 41–50 tended to report the highest awareness scores, likely reflecting longer exposure to Salesian formation. This connects with findings by Mohamad and Sihes (2019) and Madrigal and Oracion (2018), who observed that educators deepen their grasp of school values through accumulated experience. Younger teachers (20–30 years old) reported slightly lower but still very high awareness levels, consistent with early-career development patterns described by Ciriello (1996) and Ingersoll and Strong (2011). Nevertheless, statistical tests confirmed no significant differences across demographic groups, highlighting the strength of institutional formation processes.

Teachers’ Extent of Practice of the Salesian Preventive System

Teachers also demonstrated a very great extent of practice of the SPS across all pillars. This suggests that knowledge about the SPS is not merely conceptual but actively translated into classroom interactions, pastoral relationships, and school culture. Among the pillars, Loving-Kindness consistently received the highest practice scores, highlighting the relational and affective dimension of Salesian pedagogy—a dimension foundational to Don Bosco’s method.

Although the Religion pillar scored slightly lower than the others, it still fell within the “Very Great” range, suggesting strong but varied expressions of spiritual accompaniment among teachers. Differences in comfort levels with spiritual formation roles, diverse personal faith backgrounds, or varying responsibilities in pastoral ministry may contribute to this pattern, consistent with the variation noted in Philippine Catholic education studies (Banusing & Bual, 2020; Cena & Bual, 2021).

As with awareness, no significant differences in practice were found across demographic categories. This indicates that the SPS is practiced broadly and consistently among teachers regardless of age, sex, years of service, or departmental assignment. Such uniform practice reflects the strength of institutional systems that promote common pedagogical expectations across all personnel.

Relationship Between Teachers’ Awareness and Practice

One of the most important findings of this study is the strong and significant correlation between teachers’ understanding and their practice of the SPS, with Spearman’s rho coefficients ranging from 0.685 to 0.890. This

confirms that greater awareness is associated with more frequent and deeper application of SPS principles. The strength of these correlations underscores theoretical claims made in the Introduction:

- Teacher Thinking Theory (Clark & Yinger, 1977) posits that teachers' beliefs and knowledge directly shape their actions.
- Pajares (1992) and Fang (1996) emphasize that teacher cognition is a powerful predictor of classroom behavior.

In the context of Salesian education, this means that teachers who thoroughly understand Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness are more likely to embody these principles in their day-to-day interactions with learners. The findings strengthen the argument that continuous formation, reflection, and shared mission awareness are central to sustaining the Salesian character of the school.

Implications of the Findings

The consistently high awareness and strong practice levels suggest that Salesian schools maintain an effective formation system that successfully communicates Don Bosco's pedagogy to educators. This has several practical implications:

- **Formation Programs Are Effective and Should Be Sustained.** The uniformity in awareness and practice across demographic groups signals robust institutional mechanisms for onboarding and nurturing educators in the Salesian charism.
- **Younger Teachers May Benefit From Targeted Mentoring.** Although younger teachers perform well, their slightly lower awareness and practice scores indicate the value of strengthened accompaniment, peer mentoring, and experiential learning programs.
- **Spiritual Accompaniment Training May Be Enhanced.** Since Religion had the lowest (though still strong) practice scores, ongoing development in spiritual guidance and pastoral presence may strengthen this area.
- **Shared Mission Identity Is a Key Institutional Asset.** The absence of significant demographic differences reflects a school culture characterized by cohesion, shared values, and consistent expectations—an essential trait for Catholic and Salesian schools.

Limitations of the Study

This study's quantitative design provides broad patterns but does not capture the lived complexities behind teachers' interpretations and applications of the SPS. The reliance on self-reported questionnaires may introduce the potential for social desirability bias, especially in values-oriented institutions. Additionally, the sample was limited to three schools in the Philippine South Province, which may affect the generalizability of findings to other Salesian contexts in the Philippines or abroad.

Conclusion:

This study examined the level of awareness and extent of practice of the Salesian Preventive System (SPS) among basic education teachers in three Salesian schools in the Philippine South Province. The results revealed consistently very high awareness and a very great extent of practice across all three pillars of the SPS—Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness. These findings confirm that the SPS is deeply embedded in the culture, formation processes, and daily life of the participating schools, reflecting strong institutional commitment to Don Bosco's educational vision.

No significant differences were observed in awareness or practice when teachers were grouped by age, sex, years of service, or department. This uniformity indicates that SPS formation in these schools transcends demographic variables and is effectively communicated to all educators, regardless of background or experience. The strength of this shared pedagogical identity suggests that the Educative Pastoral Community (EPC) functions as a cohesive and mission-driven environment.

The study also found strong, positive, and significant correlations between teachers' awareness and their practice of the SPS. Higher understanding was associated with greater consistency in applying SPS principles. This aligns with theories of teacher cognition, which posit that beliefs and knowledge strongly influence teacher behavior. In Salesian contexts, this means that teachers who fully understand the ethos of Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness are more likely to embody these principles in their day-to-day interactions with students.

Overall, the findings affirm that Salesian educators in the Philippine South Province possess a well-internalized grasp of Don Bosco's Preventive System and translate it meaningfully into practice. The consistency of responses across demographic groups underscores the strength of the schools' shared formation and communal identity. At the same time, areas such as the practice of the Religion pillar and the slightly lower scores of younger teachers highlight opportunities for further strengthening formation programs. The study contributes empirical evidence supporting the continued relevance and vitality of the SPS in contemporary Salesian education.

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthen Ongoing Formation Programs

Given the strong correlation between awareness and practice, schools should continue and further enhance regular formation sessions on the SPS. Programs should integrate reflection, case analysis, pastoral scenarios, and opportunities for lived application of the pillars of Reason, Religion, and Loving-Kindness.

2. Provide Targeted Mentoring for Early-Career Teachers

Newer and younger teachers reported slightly lower (though still very high) levels of awareness and practice. Schools may implement mentorship programs pairing experienced Salesian educators with newer staff to deepen understanding, build confidence, and strengthen integration of SPS principles into daily practice.

3. Enhance Training in the Spiritual Dimension of the SPS

While all pillars scored "Very Great," the Religion pillar consistently had the lowest practice means. Schools may strengthen programs related to spiritual guidance, catechetical formation, sacramental preparation, and accompaniment training to support teachers in confidently fulfilling the spiritual component of Salesian education.

4. Sustain and Nurture the Shared Mission Identity

The absence of significant demographic differences in awareness and practice indicates robust institutional culture. Schools should continue community-building initiatives, cross-departmental collaboration, and EPC-wide formation to maintain and deepen this shared identity.

5. Institutionalize Reflective Practice Among Teachers

Encouraging structured reflection sessions—through learning circles, pastoral sharing, or retreat experiences—can enhance teacher self-awareness and help bridge the gap between understanding and lived practice.

6. Conduct Classroom Observations and Qualitative Follow-Up

To complement the quantitative findings, qualitative approaches such as classroom observations, focus groups, and interviews may be conducted to capture richer insights into how SPS principles are enacted in real settings.

7. Expand the Research to Other Salesian Schools and Contexts

Future studies could involve more schools across different provinces or countries to compare patterns and better understand contextual influences on SPS awareness and practice.

8. Explore Longitudinal Effects of Formation Programs

Long-term studies tracking teachers' SPS awareness and practice over several years may provide deeper insight into how formation experiences shape educator development and mission fidelity.

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